

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/mangal
hash://md5/3ed4c7f8ee88b48233d850c8991fa2dd

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/mangal, has fingerprint hash://md5/3ed4c7f8ee88b48233d850c8991fa2dd, is 101MiB in size and contains 145,989 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., preysOn) between 6,522 primary taxa (e.g., Brassica sp.) and 5,198 associated taxa (e.g., heterotheca_villosa). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

<https://mangal.io> - the ecological interaction database. <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/mangal>
2026-06-02T16:54:52.067Z hash://md5/3ed4c7f8ee88b48233d850c8991fa2dd

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5

tool name	version
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 101MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/mangal

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/mangal \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/mangal \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/mangal \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/mangal`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/mangal`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/mangal`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/mangal`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/mangal`, has fingerprint hash://md5/3ed4c7f8ee88b48233d850c8991fa2dd, is 101MiB in size and contains 145,989 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., `preysOn`) between 6,522 primary taxa (e.g., `Brassica sp.`) and 5,198 associated taxa (e.g., `heterotheca_villosa`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Brachinus explodens	preysOn	Drusilla canaliculata	(article?) {Hines_2019, doi = {10.1002/ecy.2679}, url = {https://doi.org/10.1002%2Fecy.2679}, year = 2019, month = {mar}, publisher = {Wiley}, pages = {e02679}, author = {Jes Hines and Darren P. Giling and Michael Rzanny and Winfried Voigt and Sebastian T. Meyer and Wolfgang W. Weisser and Nico Eisenhauer and Anne Ebeling}, title = {A meta-food web for invertebrate species collected in a european grassland}, journal = {Ecology}}
Abylopsis eschsoltzi	preysOn	Euterpina acutifrons	Roopnarine 2013
Lactophrys trigonus	preysOn	Euterpina acutifrons	Roopnarine 2013
Scarus vetula	preysOn	Euterpina acutifrons	Roopnarine 2013

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
preysOn	74091
mutualistOf	34914
eats	17739
parasiteOf	10594
ecologicallyRelatedTo	8651

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Brassica sp.	1017
fish fry	963
Chalcidoidea indet.	875
Argiope bruennichi	861
bombus_bifarius	814
Araniella cucurbitina	793
Salticus scenicus	730
Aculepeira ceropegia	726
Tetragnatha pinicola	668
Pterostichus minor	655
Holopedium gibberum	644
Mesocyclops edax	634
Agalenatea redii	607
Diaptomus minutus	606
Amara quenseli	601
Convolvulus arvensis	599
Amara montivaga	597
Xysticus kochi	577
Harpalus latus	574

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
heterotheca_villosa	1003
heliomeris_multiflora	900
Detritus	666

targetTaxonName	count
C. erosa	537
Lasioglossum incompletum	510
Halictus tripartitus	444
Cryptomonas ovata	440
potentilla_hippiana	426
Nephrosperma vanhoutteanum	368
Microinorganic particles	320
Acartia spinata	305
Microsetella rosea	299
Phytoplankton	295
Oncaea venusta	283
benthic detritus	281
Halictus ligatus	276
Synalpheus brevicarpus	271
Acalypta marginata	265
senecio_integerrimus	265

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
bombus_bifarius	mutualistOf	heliomeris_multiflora	357
bombus_bifarius	mutualistOf	heterotheca_villosa	299
bombus_flavifrons	mutualistOf	heliomeris_multiflora	168
thricops_septentrionalis	mutualistOf	potentilla_hippiana	132
bombus_flavifrons	mutualistOf	heterotheca_villosa	129
Convolvulus arvensis	mutualistOf	Halictus tripartitus	111
lasioglossum_spp	mutualistOf	taraxacum_officinale	104
Convolvulus arvensis	mutualistOf	Lasioglossum incompletum	103
panurginus_ineptus	mutualistOf	potentilla_hippiana	85
thricops_septentrionalis	mutualistOf	heterotheca_villosa	83
Brassica sp.	mutualistOf	Halictus tripartitus	82
Phyllocolpa leucapsis	parasiteOf	Salix cinerea	79
Brassica sp.	mutualistOf	Lasioglossum incompletum	76
thricops_septentrionalis	mutualistOf	heliomeris_multiflora	71
Brassica sp.	mutualistOf	Eupeodes fumipennis	67
Brassica sp.	mutualistOf	Halictus ligatus	64
Phyllocolpa prussica	parasiteOf	Salix cinerea	62
bombus_appositus	mutualistOf	heterotheca_villosa	61
fish fry	eats	benthic detritus	61

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

        "init=epsg:4326"
    END
    LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
        NAME "modis_nasa"
        TYPE RASTER
        OFFSITE 0 0 0
        STATUS ON
        CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
        CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

    METADATA
        "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
        "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
        "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
        "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
    END
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLOR 232 232 232
            OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
        END
    END
    LAYER
        NAME "indexed-interactions"
        TYPE POLYGON
        STATUS ON
        CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
        CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
        DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
        CLASS
            STYLE
                COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
                DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.730507727707434
                RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
                OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
            END
        END
    END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Striped spermophile ground squirrel	NONE	col	Striped spermophile ground squirrel
Affinis	NONE	col	Affinis
Ablabesmyia karelia	NONE	col	Ablabesmyia karelia
Abarenicola	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME		Abarenicola

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1866
col	class	22
col	domain	1
col	family	99
col	genus	963
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraclass	1
col	infraorder	1
col	infraphylum	1
col	kingdom	4
col	order	21
col	phylum	17
col	species	5004
col	subclass	3
col	subfamily	11
col	subgenus	46
col	suborder	5
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	155
col	superfamily	3
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	17
col	variety	23
discoverlife	NA	7649
discoverlife	species	434
gbif	NA	1903
gbif	class	20
gbif	family	103
gbif	form	3
gbif	genus	978
gbif	kingdom	5
gbif	order	24
gbif	phylum	16
gbif	species	4991
gbif	subspecies	166
gbif	variety	34
itis	NA	3999
itis	class	22
itis	division	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	family	92
itis	genus	766
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	5
itis	order	25
itis	phylum	15
itis	species	3062
itis	subclass	7
itis	subfamily	9
itis	subgenus	3
itis	suborder	6
itis	subphylum	1
itis	subspecies	43
itis	superclass	1
itis	superdivision	1
itis	superfamily	3
itis	superorder	2
itis	tribe	4
itis	variety	28
mdd	NA	8082
ncbi	NA	3347
ncbi	clade	6
ncbi	class	21
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	93
ncbi	genus	842
ncbi	infraorder	2
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	22
ncbi	phylum	16
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	3683
ncbi	subclass	7
ncbi	subfamily	12
ncbi	subgenus	29
ncbi	suborder	5
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	subspecies	9
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	3
ncbi	superkingdom	1
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	3
ncbi	varietas	7

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	NA	7170
pbdb	class	24
pbdb	family	88
pbdb	genus	466
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraclass	2
pbdb	infraorder	2
pbdb	kingdom	4
pbdb	order	26
pbdb	phylum	16
pbdb	species	260
pbdb	subclass	6
pbdb	subfamily	12
pbdb	subgenus	1
pbdb	subkingdom	2
pbdb	suborder	3
pbdb	superclass	2
pbdb	superfamily	3
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	superphylum	2
pbdb	tribe	3
pbdb	unranked clade	6
tpt	NA	7654
tpt	family	2
tpt	genus	12
tpt	species	414
wfo	NA	6561
wfo	genus	126
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	1372
wfo	subspecies	26
wfo	variety	18
worms	NA	6309
worms	class	21
worms	family	83
worms	forma	2
worms	genus	563
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	1
worms	infraphylum	1
worms	kingdom	6
worms	order	24
worms	phylum	15

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	phylum (division)	2
worms	species	1033
worms	subclass	7
worms	subfamily	2
worms	subgenus	3
worms	suborder	7
worms	subphylum	1
worms	subspecies	9
worms	superfamily	2
worms	superorder	1
worms	tribe	2
worms	variety	8

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	2123
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6236
col	SYNONYM_OF	3249
discoverlife	NONE	8853
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	297
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	233
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	23
gbif	NONE	2207
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7000
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	3318
itis	NONE	4418
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4165
itis	SYNONYM_OF	754
mdd	NONE	9079
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	110
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	2
ncbi	NONE	3742
ncbi	SAME_AS	5099
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	548
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	16

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
pbdb	NONE	7770
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1508
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	289
tpt	NONE	8738
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	626
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	81
wfo	NONE	7567
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	580
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1277
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	182
worms	NONE	6977
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2120
worms	SYNONYM_OF	397

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected

behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T08:39:38Z	note	found malformed doi [2433/156407]
2026-06-03T08:39:38Z	note	found malformed doi [2433/156407]
2026-06-03T08:39:38Z	note	found malformed doi [2433/156407]
2026-06-03T08:39:38Z	note	found malformed doi [2433/156407]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found malformed doi [2433/156407]	501

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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